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Research Article

PREVALENCE OF OBESITY AMONG MEDICAL STUDENTSDr Muhammad Rizwan Khan¹, Dr Mehmooda Mehdi², Dr Anam Javaid³¹ Rural Dispensary Malal Tehsil Fateh Jang² Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur³ Mayo Hospital Lahore

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Abstract:

Obesity is a medical condition in which excess body fat has accumulated to an extent that it may have a negative effect on health. Obesity is most commonly caused by a combination of excessive food intake, lack of physical activity, and genetic susceptibility. This cross-sectional study was conducted in different medical colleges of Punjab. A total of 130 students of both gender, living in hostels were included in the study. A predefined proforma was shared with the students. The data about weight, height, eating habits etc. was collected. All the data was collected and analyzed in SPSS 25.0. The mean age of the students was 22.87 ± 1.56 years with maximum age of 23 years and minimum age of 20 years. Out of 130, seventy (53.85%) were male students and 60 (46.15) were female students. The mean BMI was 22.12 ± 1.34 kg/m² with minimum BMI of 20.32 kg/m² and the maximum BMI of 30.43 kg/m². Five students (3.85%) were class I obese, twenty five (19.23%) were overweight, eighty eight (67.69%) were having normal BMI and twelve (9.23%) were underweight.

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INTRODUCTION:

Obesity is a medical condition in which excess body fat has accumulated to an extent that it may have a negative effect on health. People are generally considered obese when their body mass index (BMI), a measurement obtained by dividing a person's weight by the square of the person's height, is over 30 kg/m²; the range 25–30 kg/m² is defined as overweight. Some East Asian countries use lower values. Obesity increases the likelihood of various diseases and conditions, particularly cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, obstructive sleep apnea, certain types of cancer, osteoarthritis, and depression (1).

Obesity is most commonly caused by a combination of excessive food intake, lack of physical activity, and genetic susceptibility. A few cases are caused primarily by genes, endocrine disorders, medications, or mental disorder. The view that obese people eat little yet gain weight due to a slow metabolism is not medically supported. On average, obese people have a greater energy expenditure than their normal counterparts due to the energy required to maintain an increased body mass (2).

Obesity is mostly preventable through a combination of social changes and personal choices. Changes to diet and exercising are the main treatments. Diet quality can be improved by reducing the consumption of energy-dense foods, such as those high in fat or sugars, and by increasing the intake of dietary fiber. Medications can be used, along with a suitable diet, to reduce appetite or decrease fat absorption. f diet, exercise, and medication are not effective, a gastric balloon or surgery may be performed to reduce stomach volume or length of the intestines, leading to feeling full earlier or a reduced ability to absorb nutrients from food (3).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted in different medical colleges of Punjab. A total of 130 students of both gender, living in hostels were included in the study. A predefined proforma was shared with the students. The data about weight, height, eating habits etc. was collected. All the data was collected and analyzed in SPSS 25.0. The qualitative variables were presented as frequency and percentage. The quantitative variables were presented as mean and standard deviations.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the students was 22.87±1.56 years with maximum age of 23 years and minimum age of 20 years. Out of 130, seventy (53.85%) were male students and 60 (46.15) were female students. The mean BMI was 22.12±1.34 kg/m² with minimum BMI of 20.32 kg/m² and the maximum BMI of 30.43 kg/m². Five students (3.85%) were class I obese,

twenty five (19.23%) were overweight, eighty eight (67.69%) were having normal BMI and twelve (9.23%) were underweight.

DISCUSSION:

The rate of obesity also increases with age at least up to 50 or 60 years old and severe obesity in the United States, Australia, and Canada is increasing faster than the overall rate of obesity. The OECD has projected an increase in obesity rates until at least 2030, especially in the United States, Mexico and England with rates reaching 47%, 39% and 35% respectively.

The main treatment for obesity consists of weight loss via dieting and physical exercise. Dieting, as part of a lifestyle change, produces sustained weight loss, despite slow weight regain over time. Intensive behavioral interventions combining both dietary changes and exercise are recommended (4).

Several diets are effective. In the short-term low carbohydrate diets appear better than low fat diets for weight loss. In the long term, however, all types of low-carbohydrate and low-fat diets appear equally beneficial. A 2014 review found that the heart disease and diabetes risks associated with different diets appear to be similar. Promotion of the Mediterranean diets among the obese may lower the risk of heart disease. Decreased intake of sweet drinks is also related to weight-loss. Success rates of long-term weight loss maintenance with lifestyle changes are low, ranging from 2–20%. Dietary and lifestyle changes are effective in limiting excessive weight gain in pregnancy and improve outcomes for both the mother and the child. Intensive behavioral counseling is recommended in those who are both obese and have other risk factors for heart disease (5, 6).

CONCLUSION:

In our study, some of the students were overweight and some were having class I obesity. Practices and standards are needed to modify their lifestyle. Further studies should be conducted in this regard.

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